

Bioeconomy definition – working paper (11/2023)

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The bioeconomy is designed to reduce the entropic degradation of natural resources by a consumption-minimized and circular utilization of feedstock, based on transdisciplinary knowledge-creation through plural ontologies of global lifeworlds, and aimed at intergenerational justice and fairness across the world.

Explanation and sources

The currently dominant approaches to bioeconomy focus on the replacement of fossil resources by biobased ones (“substitutional bioeconomy”), and have been criticized to

- (a) neglect its ecological consequences and worsen an already dire situation (Székács 2017; Schutter et al. 2019; Erb and Gingrich 2022),
- (b) foot on an inherently unsustainable ideology in pursuing continuous growth (Giampietro 2019; Hickel and Kallis 2020; Eversberg et al. 2023), and
- (c) entrench global inequalities and erode societal institutions and democratic foundations through unquestioningly utilizing established power relations and dynamics (Birch 2006; Goven and Pavone 2015; Jessop 2012; Backhouse et al. 2022; Ramcilovic-Suominen 2022).

If a bioeconomy were to be sustainable, it must first adapt its *modus operandi* to the natural laws of biophysical reality lest it wants to risk collapsing civilization (UNEP 2016; Herrington 2021). The most general principle to guide economic activity on a path of sustainability is to keep its impact below the planet’s capacity to compensate for it, which can comprehensibly be indicated by the state of system-wide entropy (Georgescu-Roegen 1971; Giampietro 2019). Only the lowest possible entropy can sustain life on earth as long as possible, which means reducing the amount of material throughput (any material, especially non-biogenic) as much as possible (Georgescu-Roegen 1977; D’Alisa et al. 2015; Spash 2020).

As this is in stark contrast to the paradigms of current mainstream political economics, a sustainable bioeconomy cannot rest on the same knowledge-base, and it can therefore not generate knowledge from the perspective of those in power or possession of wealth (Sum 2009; Lüthmann 2020; Backhouse and Lorenzen 2021). Instead, the expedient approach is a transdisciplinary science which seeks the research questions for transformational knowledge in the quotidian challenges of citizens’ lives, thus respecting the plural perspectives on real-world applications, requirements, rights, claims and desires for a good life (Stirling 2011; Knierim et al. 2018; Ramcilovic-Suominen et al. 2022; Giuntoli et al. 2023).

Although the substitutional bioeconomy has delivered tools to make new or extended use of a fragile feedstock (Bugge et al. 2016; Meyer 2017; Vivien et al. 2019), it has neither addressed the demands and expectations these tools should help satisfy, nor the mechanisms that shape their construal and construction (Birch 2012). To formulate alternatives to the evidently destructive economic paradigms underlying this bioeconomy, their purpose must be questioned: What is the goal of economic activity? What is a good life and wellbeing? What is a sustainable relation to nature? These are questions an economy answers not as a system, but as an ethics (Heidenreich 2012; Alvey 2000), so that the Bioeconomy can holistically aim for integrated sustainability of both human and non-human nature.

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